

SKCMDb

The concept of the Slovak Comprehensive Music Database, a collaborative knowledge base of all music ever made on the territory of the Slovak Republic

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Music is one of the most data-driven industries in the world. For over a decade, AI algorithms have recommended music for streaming subscribers; festival organisers and radio stations use AI algorithms to select artists and songs to be performed. Worryingly, some service providers are appearing in places that are used to provide artists with income from AI-generated music.

Most Slovak music composers, performers, labels, tour managers, talent agents, and publishers struggle in the big data and AI-driven global music business. They are either working as freelancers, individuals, or in very small companies that need to gain knowledge or data engineers, not even an IT department at their disposal. They are disadvantaged compared to the major labels and their publishers, who employ an army of data scientists to help their rooster.

The idea of the SKCMDb is to create a public-private partnership that helps the small Slovak music businesses and individual artists' ensembles remain visible and competitive in the era of big data, machine learning recommenders, and generative AI.

Open Call for Cooperation

For individual artists, bands, ensembles

Individual artists and their groups must be on hundreds of fast-changing online platforms. With every new music release, they must provide correct titles, registration numbers, cover art, royalty data, and identifiers many times. Worse still, as digital services change, hundreds of information points often need to be updated. This is a tedious and often impossible task for self-releasing artists, their heirs, or small labels without a large documentation unit. The result is missed recommendations, being left out of curated playlists and radio shows, missing performance opportunities, and often royalty payments.

While collective management organisations like SOZA have a lawful mandate to help on radio and television, their current legal mandate is limited to streaming services and completely excludes platforms like MusicBrainz, Wikipedia, or social media pages.

The SKCMDb would like to offer a collective, public-private partnership to help. Our technology partner, REPRES and academic computer scientists are looking for ways to automate these procedures as much as possible and involve the community of music librarians, who are the best-trained people to document creative works in this service. Our aim is to use the data layer of the World Wide Web, the so-called semantic web, or the knowledge graphs, to synchronise the correct data about Slovak artists, labels, music works and sound recording releases automatically to these web services.

An important part of our work is understanding the legal situation and the application of GDPR to make our system safe and legal from a data protection point of view without compromising the huge savings

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we could make for individual artists in promoting their work. Because none of the Slovak music organisations have a full legal mandate to make this exciting, time- and cost-saving service available without further consent from artists or their legal representatives, we will work out a system of carefully designed opt-in and opt-out features to handle data in this modern, automated way. Our service is under testing and is available for free beta testing by labels or individuals upon explicit GDPR consent signed by the artist or the representative.

For small music businesses

For small companies, we would like to provide shared IT, data, and knowledge services to avoid wrangling large numbers of difficult datasets and tables daily because such work is expensive, tedious, and error-prone. We want to ensure that labels, publishers, concert and festival promoters can work more with music and the audiences and less with IT and documentation tasks that computers do much cheaper, better, and faster. We would like to offer new services based on a public-private partnership involving music libraries, the Hudobné centrum, and SOZA to help music businesses process, correct, validate, and communicate correct data and information about their artists, works, recordings and performances.

For music libraries

Music libraries themselves are not supported by the latest, most advanced semantic technologies, and they are often understaffed. We would like to involve them in this public-private partnership by providing open, free data processing, enriching and linking to keep their catalogues up-to-date and usable. We would also like to advertise their services with making music sheets, music books and recordings more findable in their collections.

Radio stations, festivals, schools

Many radio station managers and editors were unhappy when the Slovak legislation introduced mandatory Slovak quotas for their broadcasting. Many complained that they needed help finding relevant Slovak music suitable and liked by their audience.

We believe that Slovakia has a lot more good music to offer that radio editors immediately know. They suffer from the same problem that makes Slovak music so little visible on digital streaming platforms (DSPs): many self-releasing artists and small labels or publishers struggle to keep up with providing the necessary updates, data, and profiles of the changing digital music platforms. On the other hand, radio stations can less and less afford to pay for music curators and rely more and more on similar playlist creator algorithms that YouTube, Spotify and other DSPs use. We want to help them.

In our *Feasibility Study On Promoting Slovak Music In Slovakia & Abroad* (available in Slovak and English) Antal (2020c), we piloted an AI-driven application aimed at radio editors, who could modify their existing playlist (or high-rotation list) using a simple slider to increase the Slovak-language or the Slovak-origin content gradually to meet the quota. We think that this application, Listen Local, can help parents and music educators, too, to find suitable Slovak music among the international offerings that children, young and older people like.

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The study is available for download in Slovak and English Antal (2020c)

Algorithmic recommenders that follow a regulatory or educational goal are called goal-based recommendation systems. We aim to feed ethical, trustworthy, goal-based apps with reliable data about the diversity of Slovakia's music. Slovakia has a rich, diverse musical heritage and new production that anybody can love.

Application Layer

Listen Local Applications and Trustworthy AI Apps

Our Demo Application, which was developed with a microgrant of the Slovak Arts Council, we modified the Spotify recommender system to change the weekly recommendations of the user with a user-required (10-20-30...100%) Slovak language, or Slovak origin context. As a demo application, it only recognised a relatively small part of the Slovak repertoire, and iteratively changed Spotify's recommendations via the Spotify API for Developers. This simple application served a powerful demonstration tool, but due to its simplicity was not particularly suitable for bringing it into educational contexts; and it was only working with one DSP and only on web browsers.

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ListenLocal Demo App by Reprez. B.V.

Playlist: This Is Adele

	artist name	album name	track name	track id
1	Adele	25	When We Were Young	0cj2joJcY6b4XSRfj2eZOI
2	Adele	21	Set Fire to the Rain	3CKCZ9pFwAfoMZIMncA1Nc
3	Adele	Rolling In The Deep	Rolling in the Deep	5xPazRvyrkVootu8pM9vUG
4	Adele	25	Hello	4aeb8r4JAihzJQR0CilZJv
5	Adele	21	Someone Like You	6QPKYGnAW9QozVz2dSWqRg
6	Adele	25	Send My Love (To Your New Lover)	4BHzQ9C00ceJxfG16AINWb
7	Adele	19	Make You Feel My Love	7rPLZ8Krm6CZlbraFUlnWZ
8	Adele	19	Chasing Pavements (Live at Hotel Cafe)	5gcj6l37gMBeSAjFnSkEWh
9	Adele	25	All I Ask	6Hbl4e2Y2f6HYVv6r04M4W
10	Adele	25	Water Under the Bridge	4vb4mFvYsr2h6enhjJsq9Y

id
email
country SK

Choose Playlist
 This Is Adele
 This Is Zaz

Copy Print Download

Previous 1 2 3 Next

Set Recommendation Parameters!
made in Slovakia ratio: 0% 50% 100%
of which Slovak language: 0% 50% 100%
made in The Netherlands ratio: 5% 50%
made in Hungary ratio: 0% 50%

Data Coordination

Authority files or shared authority control resource

The most frequent reason for artists not being recommended to the right audience, missing payments, or being left out of streaming or radio playlists is some data problem. The most frequent of them is mistyping a name or a foreign computer misreading a Slovak diacritics (', , ^)¹. Or the fact that an artist's married name or a group's name changed. When making our *Feasibility Study On Promoting Slovak Music In Slovakia & Abroad*, we found that even among the most famous artists, 55% of the cases had some smaller or more significant data error that caused recommendations to fail or, worse, payments to go missed or late.

For decades, public and national libraries have tried to avoid such problems by creating authority files that show the possible name variations of individuals, ensembles, orchestras, and bands and suggest the correct form.

¹ The Slovak written language uses four diacritics to extend the Latin alphabet: the ˇmákčeň, the ´acute accent, the ¨diaeresis umlaut and the ^circumflex.

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← → ↻ [viaf.org/viaf/123337893/#Štátna_filharmónia_\(Košice,_Slovensko\)](http://viaf.org/viaf/123337893/#Štátna_filharmónia_(Košice,_Slovensko)) 🔍 🏠 ☆ 📄

Štátna filharmónia Košice profesionálny symfonický orchester Košic 🇸🇰

VIAF ID: 123337893 (Corporate)
Permalink: <http://viaf.org/viaf/123337893>

☰ Preferred Forms

- 🇳🇱 110 2 _ †a [CSSR State Philharmonic Orchestra](#)
- 🇧🇪 110 2 _ †a [CSSR State Philharmonic Orchestra](#)
- 🇸🇰 110 2 _ †a [Štátna filharmónia \(Košice, Slovakia\)](#)
- 🇸🇰 110 2 _ †a [Štátna filharmónia \(Košice, Slovakia\)](#)
- 🇨🇦 110 2 _ †a [Štátna filharmónia \(Košice, Slovaquie\)](#)
- 🇸🇰 210 || †a [Štátna filharmónia Košice](#)
- 🇸🇰 110 2 _ †a [Štátna filharmónia Košice](#)
- 🇩🇪 110 2 _ †a [Štátna filharmónia Košice](#)
- 🇸🇰 210 0 2 †a [Štátna filharmónia †c Košice, Slovensko](#)
- 🇸🇰 110 2 _ †a [Štátna filharmónia Košice](#)

One of the aims of the SKCMDb is to serve as a shared authority control system among Slovakia's rights management organisations, music libraries, the Hudobné center and the Hudobny Fond, and Wikimedia Slovensko which controls the Slovak version of Wikipedia and Wikidata. We would also like to involve in this system the National Library.

Note

Wikidata, the semantic database was originally developed to coordinate and improve data on the many language versions of Wikipedia. As an open-source and excellent tool, many national libraries, national museums and EU organisations started to use it. Countries like Luxembourg, France, Germany, Sweden use it for the coordination of authority files via Wikidata or its graph database engine Wikibase². Our aim is to move the authority file coordination to Wikibase, too, because it will give librarians and archivists an easy-to-use and globally well understood graphical interface to share their work with each other. We reached out to the Wikimedia Foundation and *WMSK*, former official legal name *Wikimedia Slovenská republika* to not only use their open source product, i.e., Wikibase for authority control reconciliation but as a tool to push our knowledge to Wikidata—this way corrections and new information will be used by global streaming platforms and industry databases in a few days.

² The use of Wikidata is getting more and more common among knowledge organisations and even EU organisations for the coordination of namespaces or authority files. Originally developed as a reconciliation tool for Wikipedia, Europeana already recognised its value for pan-European data harmonisation in 2015. Since then, several European countries have used it as a decentralised, curated, shared authority control system. We think that VIAF is the most suitable authority control, but the flexibility and functionality of Wikidata make it a worthy parallel system in itself (Bianchini, Bargioni, and Pellizzari di San Girolamo 2021; Veen 2019; Rossenova, Duchesne, and Blümel 2022). (Fagerving 2023).

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Because of the repeated problems with name mistakes, Spotify and Apple have announced that they will make authority files mandatory to upload music to their systems. We would like to provide Slovak artists, labels, and publishers with a simple, one-stop-shop and free or very cheap system to do this in any known library, streaming and music information system in the world.

Business register

Producing better statistics on music would benefit every artist, label, talent agent, and publisher. Currently, music is disadvantaged because, in the absence of reliable figures on the work of artists, employment, income, prices, and gross value added, policymakers do not know how important music is in the country's touristic service offering; they often underestimate the amount of taxes paid by the music community and overestimate the subsidies received. The *Slovak Music Industry Report* showed that compared to the car manufacturing industry, for example, music enterprises pay significantly more taxes on their turnover or profit. More accurate and credible data is needed to advocate for better policies, more just taxation, or to help access green financing for music businesses.

Slovakia is among the few European countries that have extended its national statistical system with satellite accounts to better measure income, value-added and employment in the cultural and creative industries³. Unfortunately, there is no separate music account available, and we do not have important business and policy KPIs for music.

³ Read more on the Slovak cultural and creative satellite accounting system in *The Summary Results of the Satellite Account on Culture and Creative Industry Of the Slovak Republic (2015-2020)* (Horecka and Némethová 2022). Read more about our plans to extend the current satellite account system with higher quality music statistics: *Pilot Program for Novel Music Industry Statistical Indicators in the Slovak Republic* (Antal 2023) and *Economy of music in Europe: Novel data collection methods and indicators* (Antal, Kmety Barteková, and Remeňová 2023).

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The data coordination model discussed with SOSR, IKP, Hudobné centrum, SOZA, Reprex and EUBA on 11 October 2023.

We aim to use the authority control part of the SKCMDb as a business register for statistical data coordination. The business register will be optional to use for freelancers and private persons and will be based on the registers of rights management organisations in the case of labels and publishers (which are public based on the Slovak copyright law.)

Using the SKCMDb as a business register will enable the Slovak music stakeholders and the Statistical Office of the Slovak Republic to create the most accurate official statistics on how musicians live and earn their living in Europe—a research and innovation grant from the European Commission funds this programme. Our approach can be replicated for the film industry, galleries, libraries, archives and museums (GLAM), or other creative industries.

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Note

SOZA has advocated for better, more music-friendly economic policies for many years. The *Slovak Music Industry Report* (which is available in Slovak only), and the subsequent, comparative CEE Music Industry Report were seen all over Europe as one of the best and most successful works Antal (2020a). Following the economic development program described in this book, SOZA became one of those collective management societies that increased more the payouts to their members in Europe. As the best example, SOZA and its partner, REPRES, successfully gained a European grant to extend this program into the Open Music Europe program.

SOZA, REPRES, and the Open Music Europe Consortium signed a *Memorandum of Understanding* with the Ministry of Culture⁴ to make an effort to support a better implementation of the Slovak cultural policy strategy (*Stratégia kultúry a kreatívneho priemyslu Slovenskej republiky 2030*) and the Slovak sustainable development goals (*Vízia a stratégia rozvoja Slovenska do roku 2030 - dlhodobá stratégia udržateľného rozvoja*) (Ministerstva investícií, regionálneho rozvoja a informatizácie Slovenskej republiky 2020; Ministerstvo kultúry Slovenskej republiky 2023). This open collaboration is available for all music organisations and businesses of the Slovak Republic and even beyond. We want to show how our methods can be applied in the audiovisual sector or the GLAM (galleries, libraries, archives and museums) sectors, too.

⁴ *Memorandum o porozumení o využití výsledkov analýz otvorených politík v kontexte slovenského kultúrneho a kreatívneho priemyslu a sektorových verejných politík v spolupráci s konzorciom pre výskum a inovácie s názvom OpenMuse*. [Memorandum of Understanding on utilizing the Open Policy Analysis results of the OpenMuse Research and Innovation Consortium in the context of Slovak cultural and creative industries and sectors' public policies] (Open Music Europe 2023; Ministerstvo kultúry SR and Open Music Europe 2023)

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